

Structure and reducibility of doped by yttrium cerium dioxide nanoparticles and (111) surface

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Abstract

Using periodic density functional calculations we studied local structure and preferable locations of yttrium cations and oxygen vacancies in Y-doped cerium dioxide. We employed three kinds of models – a slab of CeO₂(111) surface and two ceria nanoparticles of different sizes and shapes. In the slab models, which represent (111) surface of ceria and the corresponding extended terraces on the facets of its nanoparticles, doping Y³⁺ cations are calculated to be preferably located close to each other. They tend to surround a subsurface oxygen vacancy occurring due to the charge balance. Such a general behavior is not found for the nanoparticle models, where structural flexibility and the presence of various low-coordinated surface centers seem to be crucial and suppress most of the trends. Configurations with four Y³⁺ cations are calculated to be particularly stable, when they combined two of the most stable configurations with two Y³⁺ cations. Yet, no clear trend is found about the preferential spatial distribution of the Y³⁺ pairs – they can be stable both isolated and close to each other. In general, the doping by yttrium does not change notably the reducibility of ceria systems, but it selectively facilitates oxygen vacancy formation at the ceria surface, compared to the pristine ceria. Yttrium cations also slightly increase the basicity of the nearby oxygen centers with respect to stoichiometric ceria surface.

1. Introduction

In recent years ceria-based materials have gained a tremendous interest from both fundamental science and commercial points of view. In particular, ceria attracted great attention due to its crucial role as a catalyst component for numerous catalytic applications. The ever-growing interest is demonstrated by the vast numbers of publications, starting from the review by Trovarelli in 1996,¹ following with two books in 2002² and 2013³ and comprising many reviews⁴⁻⁶ as well as special issue of Catalysis Today in 2015.⁷

Many studies have revealed the applicability of ceria as a support in different catalysts due to its well-known high oxygen storage capacity (OSC).¹⁻³ It is a reducible oxide and O vacancies can be created in ceria at elevated temperatures. This process accompanied by reduction of two Ce⁴⁺ cations to Ce³⁺ state per each O vacancy can be reversible depending on the conditions.¹⁻⁴

Doping of ceria is a commonly exploited approach for tailoring its redox properties and concomitantly affecting the catalytic behavior.⁸ The presence of aliovalent dopants⁹ causes appearance of extrinsic defects that play key role in the performance of many catalytic processes. Of particular importance for both technological applications and fundamental research are CeO₂ materials doped with rare-earth elements including yttrium. When CeO₂ is doped by a trivalent metal oxide, such as Y₂O₃, the initial structure contains O vacancies created in order to compensate the effective negative charge induced by the substitution of Ce⁴⁺ with Y³⁺. Thus, a distortion is induced in the cubic matrix of the resulting Y₂O₃-CeO₂ mixed oxide. Beneficial role of the yttrium doping on the activity of ceria for soot combustion has been demonstrated by Atribak et al.¹⁰ Considering the abundance of yttrium resource, She et al. have studied the effect of Y addition (0 – 5 wt.%) to CuO/CeO₂ catalyst on the water-gas shift activity.¹¹ The highest catalytic activity was exhibited by the catalyst doped with 2 wt.% Y. The role of different synthesis routes for the preparation of Y-doped ceria and of various Y amounts in the performance of the preferential CO oxidation in excess of hydrogen (PROX) on supported gold catalysts has been discussed by Ilieva et al.¹² Irrespective of the preparation method, very similar CO conversion degrees were measured over samples with 1-5 wt.% Y₂O₃ in the temperature range 80–120 °C, which is of interest for fuel cells operation. A relatively low activity observed for doped ceria samples with 7.5 wt.% Y₂O₃ content was assigned to hindered oxygen supply due to the assumed ordering of surface oxygen vacancies around segregated Y³⁺. Similarly, no improvement of the PROX activity and stability of gold catalysts supported on Y-doped ceria was reported by Jardim et al.¹³, who explained this

result by the surface segregation of the high amount of used Y_2O_3 (30 wt.%).

Several theoretical investigations have been focused on the understanding of ceria doping by yttrium and lanthanide metals. For instance, Dholabhai et al. have studied oxygen vacancy formation and migration in Pr- and Gd-doped ceria with the help of methods based on density functional theory (DFT).^{14,15} The local ordering of oxygen vacancies in $\text{Ce}_{1-x}\text{Y}_x\text{O}_{2-x/2}$ with $x = 0.04, 0.08, 0.11, 0.18,$ and 0.26 (corresponding to 2, 4, 6, 10, and 15 mol. % Y_2O_3) has been investigated by analyzing the data of experimental measurements (impedance spectroscopy and neutron diffraction) and ab initio based molecular dynamics simulations.¹⁶ It was concluded that ionic conductivity of Y-doped ceria decreased with increasing Y_2O_3 amount due to ordering of anion vacancies. The dopant distribution in ceria of rare earth oxides and the oxygen ion conductivity of these systems were also investigated by Grieshammer et al. combining DFT and Monte Carlo studies.¹⁷ Hu and Metiu¹⁸ have modelled doping of ceria (111) surface by a single Y^{3+} cation with no charge compensating O vacancy, which would required an introduction of a second dopant cation. Such single dopant lowers the O vacancy formation energy by more than 1.2 eV. Surprisingly, in another DFT based study of yttrium doped CeO_2 (110) surface¹⁹ it was proposed a peculiar arrangement of the charge distribution in a structure with two Y^{3+} and one O vacancy – one Ce^{3+} cation and O^- anion were found. Such charge distribution was reported as the most stable without providing the energetics of the conventional arrangement containing just Ce^{4+} and O^{2-} ions. Yet, it will be interesting for catalytic applications and beyond to understand the influence of Y^{3+} cations on the reducibility of stoichiometric $\text{CeO}_2/\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3$ systems and to clarify whether nanostructuring changes the behavior of these systems with respect to the surface models.

In the current study, we model various structures, where Y^{3+} cations replace Ce^{4+} cations on/in CeO_2 (111) slab and two ceria nanoparticle models with different size ($\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ and $\text{Ce}_{40}\text{O}_{80}$) at low Y:Ce atomic ratios of 3.9 % and 8.0 % for the slab model and 10.5 % and 23.5 %, as well as 5.3 % and 11.1 % for the two nanoparticle models, respectively. The goals of the present work are to clarify, whether yttrium dopants prefer to segregate or be distantly distributed among cerium cations and to estimate the changes of the reducibility of ceria in the presence of Y^{3+} cations. It is also interesting to trace the differences in the behavior of the slab, which can represent larger particles, and of the nanoparticle models, where irregularities and low coordinated surface positions (edges and corners) are more abundant.

2. Computational Details and Models

The calculations are performed using a periodic plane-wave DFT method with PW91²⁰

exchange-correlation functional of a generalized-gradient (GGA) type as implemented in the VASP program.²¹⁻²³ The stoichiometric and reduced ceria is described within the so-called GGA+U approach,^{24,25} in which on-site Columbic interaction with $U = 4 \text{ eV}$ ²⁶ is included. Our test calculations without applying the U correction for systems not containing Ce^{3+} cations showed that the relative stability of the structures remains similar to that obtained with $U = 4 \text{ eV}$. A plane-wave basis with a 415 eV cut-off for the kinetic energy and projector-augmented wave²³ description of core-valence electron interactions are employed. During geometry optimization all atoms were allowed to relax locally until the maximum forces acting on each atom become less than 0.02 eV/\AA . We performed only Γ -point calculations. Spin-polarization was taken into account, when O vacancies were modeled, since this leads to formation of Ce^{3+} cations, which have unpaired electrons. The oxygen vacancy formation energy E_{vac} was calculated with respect to a half of the energy of O_2 molecule in its triplet state as follows:

$$E_{\text{vac}} = E(\text{Ce}_x\text{O}_{2x-1}) + 1/2 \times E(\text{O}_2) - E(\text{Ce}_x\text{O}_{2x})$$

$$E_{\text{vac}} = E(\text{Ce}_{x-2}\text{Y}_2\text{O}_{2x-2}) + 1/2 \times E(\text{O}_2) - E(\text{Ce}_{x-2}\text{Y}_2\text{O}_{2x-1})$$

CeO₂(111) surface slab model. The CeO₂(111) surface is modelled with a slab Ce₅₄O₁₀₈ of three CeO₂ (nine atomic) layers and a 3×6 surface cell with cell parameters: $a = 13.224 \text{ \AA}$, $b = 19.836 \text{ \AA}$, $c = 19.353 \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$, $\gamma = 60^\circ$. The lateral dimensions of the cells were fixed according to the experimental bulk geometry ($a = 541 \text{ pm}$).²⁷ The notation of the modelled structures is given in the sections below, where the corresponding structures are discussed.

Ce₂₁O₄₂ and Ce₄₀O₈₀ nanoparticle models. We employed a small ceria nanoparticle Ce₂₁O₄₂ with a diameter of about 1 nm,²⁸⁻³⁴ located in a cubic $2.0 \times 2.0 \times 2.0 \text{ nm}$ unit cell, as well as a larger Ce₄₀O₈₀ nanoparticle with the diameter of about 1.5 nm^{30,35-38} positioned in a unit cell with the rectangular parallelepiped shape and dimensions: $2.2 \times 1.9 \times 1.9 \text{ nm}$. In these models, the distance between the neighboring images in the periodic unit cells is at least 0.9 nm. The notation of the modelled structures is given in the sections below, where the corresponding structures are discussed.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Yttrium-doped CeO₂(111) surface

For regular CeO₂(111) surface we modeled various structures of two types of stoichiometric systems – with two and four cerium ions substituted by yttrium ones. In addition, for the former type of models we computed oxygen vacancy formation energies.

3.1.1. Stoichiometric systems containing two yttrium ions

We have modeled 27 structures, in which two Y³⁺ cations replaces two Ce⁴⁺ cations. In order to balance the charge of the system one O atom was removed from the structure shown in Fig. 1 (see also Table 1). We considered structures with O vacancy created in three different positions: (i) in the surface layer (SL, O_{SL}); (ii) in the first subsurface layer (FS, O_{FS}); (iii) in the second subsurface layer (SS, O_{SS}). Positions of cerium cations replaced by Y³⁺ are specified in Figure 1. To denote the resulting structures the position of the created O vacancy is followed (in parentheses) by the positions of the replaced Ce⁴⁺ ions.

The stability of the modeled structures (Table 1) depends on both the positions of the two yttrium centers and of the O vacancy and varies by up to 1.0 eV. The three most stable essentially iso-energetic structures, O_{FS}(1B,2C), O_{FS}(2C,2D) and O_{SS}(2C,2D) contain at least one subsurface Y³⁺ cation and the O vacancy either in the subsurface or in the second subsurface layers. The next two structures O_{FS}(1A,1B) and O_{SL}(1A,1B) with both surface yttrium cations at the surface are by ca. 0.3 eV less stable. In all most stable structures destabilized by up to 0.5 eV the two Y³⁺ cations are located in neighboring sites separated by up to ca. 420 pm. Note, however, that there are structures, which completely or partially have the above features but are notably less stable (see brown triangles in Fig. 2A). Figure 2B (brown triangles), including all modeled relative locations of the yttrium centers, also shows a lack of a clear relation between the relative stability and the location of the two dopant cations on the surface, in the subsurface layer or in the both positions.

Although O vacancies in the most stable structures are located on the sites neighboring yttrium centers, a general correlation between the Y-O_{vac} distances (accounted in different ways, see Fig. S4 in ESI) and the relative stability of all modeled structures cannot be found.

In order to check, if the space of the missing O can be refilled by O atom we modeled structures with an added O atom put in the position of the missing O atom in the discussed above Y-containing models. The systems were optimized as spin-polarized and neutral. All the structures with an additional O were calculated to be less stable by 0.83, 1.27 and 1.12 eV over the initial structures O_{SL}(1A,1B), O_{FS}(1B,2C) and O_{SS}(2C,2D) plus a half of gas-phase

O₂ molecule, respectively. Thus, filling by oxygen of such surface and subsurface positions of the charge compensating O vacancy is not unexpectedly energetically unfavorable up to rather high oxygen pressures.

In order to check the relative stability of the electronic state of the system reported elsewhere,¹⁹ we performed geometry optimization of the O_{SL}(1I,1J) and O_{SL}(1B,2C) structures in the fixed triplet state. In this way we obtained structures with electron density distribution, analogous to that of Ref. 19 - with one Ce³⁺ cation and partially electron deficient oxygen anions due to forced transfer of one O 2p electron to a Ce⁴⁺ cation. However, in both O_{SL}(1I,1J) and O_{SL}(1B,2C) cases this triplet state was by more than 1.4 eV less stable than the aforementioned singlet state. Thus, the spontaneous electron transfer from O²⁻ to Ce⁴⁺ ions in the yttrium-doped ceria systems appears to result in an excited state rather than in their ground state.

3.1.2. Oxygen vacancy in the systems containing two yttrium ions

In order to estimate the reducibility of ceria in the presence of two Y³⁺ cations, we modeled oxygen vacancy creation in the most stable structures with the oxygen vacancy located in the surface layer, O_{SL}(1A,1B), first subsurface layer, O_{FS}(1B,2C), and the second subsurface layer, O_{SS}(2C,2D). The O center was removed from various surface, subsurface and second subsurface (below surface Ce or Y) positions (see Fig. 3 and Table 2). In most cases the location of two Ce⁴⁺ cations reduced to Ce³⁺ is calculated to be nearby the created O vacancy. We note in passing that both the nearest-neighbor and the next-nearest-neighbor locations of two Ce³⁺ cations with respect to O vacancies resulted from DFT-based calculations for slab models of pristine ceria surfaces.^{39,40}

As a reference, we considered formation of oxygen vacancy on the surface and in the first and second subsurface layers of the undoped surface (Fig. 1). The most stable is the structure where O vacancy is in the first subsurface layer, with $E_{\text{vac}} = 2.55$ eV, close to the value of 2.48 eV from PW91+4 calculations.⁴⁰ The structures with a vacancy in the second subsurface layer or in the surface layer are by 0.22 and 0.33 eV higher in energy, respectively.

The lowest O vacancy formation energy for the Y-doped structures corresponds to O_{FS}(1B,2C)-2f, where both missing O atoms are in the first subsurface layer with $E_{\text{vac}} = 2.52$ eV, only very slightly lower than calculated for the pristine CeO₂(111) surface. The next four structures have 0.1 – 0.2 eV higher E_{vac} values and feature differently located O vacancies – combined in surface and first and second subsurface layers. This similarity in the stability of the structures with different locations of the O vacancy suggests that various spatial

distributions of the O vacancies may exist in Y-doped ceria. One should note the structure $O_{SL}(1A,1B)$ -1a with $E_{vac} = 2.61$ eV, where the both O vacancies are in the surface. This value is by 0.27 eV lower than the E_{vac} calculated for removal of the equivalent surface O atom on pristine $CeO_2(111)$ surface. This result implies that the presence of Y^{3+} can facilitate removal of surface oxygen atoms compared to those on undoped ceria surface. Thus, the difference between oxygen vacancy formation energies on the surface and in subsurface layer of the oxide is reduced to only 0.10 eV from notably larger 0.33 eV on the bare ceria surface.

The comparison of the vacancy locations in different structures suggests that two O vacancies may be either close to or far from each other, but it is not favorable to remove the O atom located between two Y^{3+} cations.

In summary, doping by Y does not influence the energy for O vacancy formation in the subsurface region. However, formation energy of a surface vacancy is facilitated compared to the undoped surface and becomes close to the formation energy of the subsurface vacancy.

This finding agrees with results of a recent experimental study of relationships between the structural features and water gas shift (WGS) activity of gold catalysts supported on Y-doped ceria (1.0, 2.5, 5.0 and 7.5 wt % Y_2O_3).⁴¹ The temperature programmed reduction measurements revealed that the doping of ceria with Y_2O_3 affected the reduction behavior. The effect is stronger when the doped ceria supports are prepared by impregnation than using co-precipitation. The improved reducibility of the gold catalysts on ceria with predominantly surface modification (impregnated samples) correlated well with a better WGS performance compared to the gold samples on the supports prepared by co-precipitation with prevailing bulk modification by Y. A nano-scale 3D electron microscopy study by Collins et al. for La-doped ceria also has shown a dominant reduction at the surface of the nanoparticles as estimated by the location of the Ce^{3+} ions.⁹

3.1.3 Stoichiometric systems with four yttrium ions

We obtained structures with four Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies by adding a pair of Y^{3+} cations to the most stable structures with two Y^{3+} cations and one O vacancy, $O_{FS}(1B,2C)$ and $O_{SS}(2C,2D)$, and creating there a new O vacancy. These added Y^{3+} cations and the new O vacancy were positioned based on the finding (*vide supra*) that pairs of Y^{3+} cations tend to stay close to each other at the oxygen vacancy. We found five lowest-energy structures of this kind with the stability range within 0.10 eV (Table 3). Some of these structures combine Y ions in the surface and the subsurface layers, while in the others both Y pairs are in the subsurface layer; O vacancies are in the subsurface or in the second subsurface layer. In

$O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{FS}(1H,2F)$ and $O_{SS}(2C,2D)/O_{SS}(2E,2F)$ Y pairs are far apart and in the other three structures (given in Table 3 in italics) the pairs are close to each other. Overall one can see from Table 3 that structures, which contain O vacancies on the surface, are less stable than those with vacancies in the first and second subsurface layers. It can be also noticed that the combinations of two stable configurations of Y^{3+} pair and an O vacancy lead to stable structures with four Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies.

3.1.4. Influence of yttrium on the basicity of surface oxygen centers

We used the most stable Y-doped structures to estimate the changes in the basicity of the surface oxygen centers. According to earlier studies O 1s core level shift correlates with the basicity of the oxygen centers as estimated by the proton affinity of that center – the less stable O 1s core level (with lower absolute energy value $E(O1s)$) corresponds to more basic oxygen center.⁴² There it was estimated that a destabilization of the O 1s core level by 1.0 eV corresponds to increase of the proton affinity of the O center by ca. 80 kJ/mol.

Oxygen atoms in the pristine $CeO_2(111)$ feature very distinct separation of the O 1s core levels – the surface and subsurface oxygen centers have $E(O1s)$ around -503.7 and -504.0 eV, respectively (see the green bullets in Fig. 4). The presence of yttrium cations and oxygen vacancy modifies the O 1s energy values (see the brown triangles and blue rhombus in Fig. 4 and Fig. S3A in ESI) and the $E(O1s)$ values become spread over a somewhat wider interval - 503.5 to -504.2 eV. For most of the oxygen centers the O 1s core level is stabilized by only up to 0.1 eV (Fig. S3A in ESI). Oxygen centers close to yttrium ions and the oxygen vacancy exhibit a more specific behavior. For the structure with both yttrium cations and oxygen vacancy in the surface layer the O 1s level of the oxygen center between two cations (in the first subsurface layer) is destabilized by 0.4 eV and the other oxygen centers around each of the dopant cations that are not neighboring the oxygen vacancy are destabilized by 0.2 eV. The most basic oxygen centers in the structure are shown in indigo in Fig. S3B in ESI; they have $E(O1s)$ by 0.2-0.4 eV lower in magnitude than the surface oxygen centers of pristine ceria, thus being somewhat more basic. On the other hand, the O1s core levels of the oxygen centers around the oxygen vacancy (shown in orange in Fig. S3B) are stabilized by 0.2 eV with respect to the corresponding centers in the pristine ceria surface.

3.2 Yttrium-doped $Ce_{21}O_{42}$ nanoparticle

As for $CeO_2(111)$ surface slab model, we modeled structures with two and four Y^{3+} cations by replacing two and four Ce^{4+} cations, respectively, using a smaller $Ce_{21}O_{42}$ nanoparticle (Fig. 5), from which one O atom was removed for charge balance for each pair of Y^{3+} cations.

There are two- and three-coordinated O centers on the nanoparticle surface, while the subsurface O centers are four-coordinated. The two-coordinated oxygen ions 1a, 1b, 1c and 1d displayed in Fig. 5 form a small (100) facet. The corresponding Ce^{4+} cations, which are a part of this facet, are denoted as 1A, 1B, 1C and 1D. The other two-coordinated O centers (1i, 1j, 1m, 1n, 1o) are located at the corner of the nanoparticle. The three-coordinated O centers are denoted as 1e, 1f, and 1l, while the subsurface centers (four-coordinated) are denoted as 2g, 2h and 2k. Due to small size of the nanoparticle, there is only one subsurface Ce^{4+} cation denoted as 2I.

3.2.1 Stoichiometric $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle containing two yttrium ions

We considered 23 structures with two Y^{3+} cations, which could be grouped by the type of the oxygen center removed from the nanoparticle. The stability of the modeled structures is evaluated by their relative energies shown in Table 4. In the most stable structure $\text{O}_{4c}(2\text{I},1\text{H})$ -2h (Fig. 6a) one of the Y^{3+} is in the only subsurface position, while another Y^{3+} is on the (111) surface facet and the vacancy is created by removing one of the two four-coordinated oxygen centers located between the Y^{3+} cations. In total, nine the most stable structures have energies within 0.20 eV. In these stable structures both Y^{3+} cations replace Ce^{4+} cations from the top two layers - (100) facet and the layer below it, i.e. in the positions denoted as A-J; in the six of the most stable structures the subsurface cationic position 2I is occupied by Y^{3+} . O vacancy in these nine structures is formed by removal of either a two-coordinated or four-coordinated oxygen center.

The calculated energies of the other 14 modeled structures are by 0.36 – 1.21 eV less stable relative to the most stable structure $\text{O}_{4c}(2\text{I},1\text{H})$ -2h. There, yttrium dopants are in all three possible cationic layers of the smaller nanoparticle. In the least stable structures with relative energies exceeding 0.80 eV both Y^{3+} cations are in surface positions (see green bullets in Fig. 2B).

In general, the energetic stability of the doped structures under scrutiny is not driven by the coordination number of the removed O center. The mutual location of two Y^{3+} cations also does not determine the stability. Hence, there is no clear correlation between the stability of a given structure and the corresponding Y-Y distance (see green bullets in Fig. 2A).

The distance between the oxygen center, which is removed, and the Y^{3+} cations is not crucial for the stability of a given $\text{Ce}_{19}\text{Y}_2\text{O}_{41}$ structure (Table 4), partly due to the geometric flexibility of the nanoparticle model. For instance, in almost the most stable structures $\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{I},1\text{A})$ -1a and $\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{I},1\text{H})$ -1a the oxygen vacancy is neighboring none or only one of Y^{3+}

cations, while in structures $O_{2c}(1A,1B)$ -1b, $O_{2c}(1K,1M)$ -1n, $O_{2c}(1K,1E)$ -1i destabilized compared to the most stable structure $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h by 0.31, 0.82 and 1.21 eV, respectively, the oxygen vacancy neighbors the both Y^{3+} ions.

3.2.2 Oxygen vacancy in the nanoparticles containing two yttrium ions

From the most stable structures with two Y^{3+} cations, $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h and $O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a, we made models with the second O vacancy by removing one of two-coordinated O centers (Table 5). Six models derived from $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h were considered: in four of them an O center was removed from the (100) facet, while in the remaining models the O center was removed from edge sites. The coordination number and the location of the second removed O center are specified, respectively, at the beginning and at the end of the structure notation. For instance, the notation $O_{2c}(O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a)-1b means that the O vacancy is created in two-coordinated position 1b of the structure $O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a. Removal of an O generates two Ce^{3+} cations. In all structures both Ce^{4+} cations, which were reduced, are positioned directly nearby the site of the removed O, except for the $O_{2c}(O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a)-1b structure, where the second removed O atom was initially bound to a surface Y^{3+} cations.

The most stable is structure $O_{2c}(O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a)-1c, where the two vacancies are located opposite to each other on the (100) facet, with $E_{vac} = 1.87$ eV. The latter is slightly lower than 2.04 eV calculated by us for the pristine $Ce_{21}O_{42}$ nanoparticle with the same locations of O vacancy and Ce^{3+} cations. Note, however, that the lowest O vacancy formation energy for the nanoparticle $Ce_{21}O_{42}$ obtained with the same computational setup, 1.67 eV,^{28,29} indicates that the presence there of Y^{3+} does not facilitate the O vacancy formation. O vacancy formation energies in the other positions of the (100) facet of the pristine $Ce_{21}O_{42}$ nanoparticle are similar 2.07 eV (1a), 2.07 eV (1b) and 2.20 eV (1d). For removal of an O center from the positions 1b, 1d and 1i of the $O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a structure the E_{vac} values are at least 0.2 eV higher than the $O_{2c}(O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a)-1c value.

For O removed from the $O_{2c}(2I,1H)$ -2h structure E_{vac} values vary from 2.01 eV to 2.85 eV. Similar to O removal from $O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a, the lowest E_{vac} values again were calculated for O removed from the positions 1i and 1c, 2.01 and 2.03 eV, respectively. Notably, we were unable to find any correlation of the distances between two O vacancies (O_{vac} - O_{vac} in Table 5) with the E_{vac} values.

3.2.3 Stoichiometric $Ce_{21}O_{42}$ nanoparticle containing four yttrium ions

We also modeled nanoparticle structures with four Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies. For that we used two the most stable structures with two Y^{3+} cations and one O vacancy, $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -

2h and $O_{2c}(2I,1A)$ -1a along with $O_{2c}(1A,1C)$ -1a structure, where both Y^{3+} ions are located on the (100) facet (see Table 4). In each of these three structures we replaced two Ce^{4+} cations by Y^{3+} ones concomitantly removing one O. These new Y^{3+} sites and O vacancy are reflected in the notation of the structures accordingly. For instance, the notation $O_{2c}(1L,1F)$ -1m/ $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h means that in the structure $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h two Ce^{4+} cations in positions 1L and 1F are replaced by Y^{3+} and the second O vacancy is formed in the position 1m. The calculated results for the $Ce_{17}Y_4O_{40}$ structures are summarized in Table 6.

There are six modeled structures with relative energies within 0.23 eV and in all of them one of the yttrium ions is located in the subsurface position denoted 2I (see Fig. 7). The stability of the other studied structures ranges between 0.29 and 2.60 eV. Note, that in several of these destabilized structures Y^{3+} also occupies the subsurface position 2I, which thus seems not to be a decisive stabilization factor of the $Ce_{17}Y_4O_{40}$ structures.

The least stable structure is $O_{4c}(1M,1O)$ -2k/ $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h, in which the four-coordinated O center is removed between the Y^{3+} ions in 2I and 1H cationic positions. As a comparison, a structure $O_{2c}(1M,1O)$ -1o/ $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h with the same four Y^{3+} positions, but instead with two-coordinated O (1o) removed, is ca. 1.7 eV more stable than $O_{4c}(1M,1O)$ -2k/ $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h. In the latter, four Y^{3+} form a triangular pyramid, inside which the 2k center is located. The distance between a Y^{3+} in the pyramid base and the top Y^{3+} is elongated by 35 pm compared to that in $O_{4c}(1M,1O)$ -1o/ $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h, as a consequence of the removal of 2k center.

Structure $O_{2c}(1B,1D)$ -1c/ $O_{2c}(1A,1C)$ -1a, where all four Y^{3+} cations are in the (100) facet and two removed O centers were located opposite to each other in the same facet, is by 0.38 eV less stable than the most stable one, $O_{2c}(1L,1F)$ -1m/ $O_{4c}(2I,1H)$ -2h.

Table 6 also shows differences between the Y-Y distances in the parent structures (with two Y^{3+} cations and one O vacancy) and the corresponding resulting structures with four Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies, ΔY -Y. In some structures (including three the most stable ones) this distance is essentially the same or changed only by up to 8 pm. However, when considering all modeled structures no clear correlation between the stability and the variation of the Y-Y distance can be derived.

In summary, the stability of the Y-doped structures based on the $Ce_{21}O_{42}$ nanoparticle is not clearly determined by only one factor, such as coordination of the removed O centers or the Y-Y and Y- O_{vac} distances. In general, one can notice that structures with one of the Y^{3+} cations located in the subsurface position are among the most stable ones.

3.3 Yttrium-doped larger Ce₄₀O₈₀ nanoparticle

3.3.1 Stoichiometric nanoparticle containing two yttrium ions

Results for modeled 26 structures based on a larger nanoparticle Ce₄₀O₈₀ with different combinations of two Y³⁺ cations and one O vacancy are shown in Table 7, see Fig. 8 for labels of the positions of the Y³⁺ cations and O vacancies. The most stable is the structure O_{2c}(1E,1K)-1a with symmetrically situated surface Y³⁺ ions at the apexes of the nanoparticle and an O center removed from a two-coordinated position in a (100) facet. In an earlier study Ce⁴⁺ cations in these apex positions were found to be reduced the most easily compared to the other Ce⁴⁺ cations in the nanoparticle Ce₄₀O₈₀.^{28,29} The next five higher in energy structures exhibit similar stability, with the relative energies in the interval 0.27 – 0.32 eV. These structures reveal different types of locations of Y³⁺ cations: *i*) in neighboring subsurface positions, O_{2c}(2H,2O)-1a; *ii*) in distant subsurface positions, O_{2c}(2H,2S)-1a; *iii*) in neighboring surface positions, O_{2c}(1B,1E)-1a; *iv*) in distant corner surface positions, O_{2c}(1L,1R)-1a; *v*) in neighboring surface and subsurface positions, O_{2c}(1F,2H)-1a. In all these structures the O vacancy is in the low-coordinated 1a surface position. During geometry optimization of several structures with an O vacancy in the subsurface 2e position, the oxygen center from position 1a moved to the vacancy site 2e. Hence, the O_{2e} vacancy became O_{1a}.

As a general trend, the structures with O vacancies generated by removing three- (1o and 1f) or four-coordinated (2h and 2l) centers are unstable; the structures become stable only when the vacancy is created in the two-coordinated O position (1a). For instance, *i*) the structure O_{2c}(2H,2O)-1a is more stable by 0.51 eV than O_{2c}(2H,2O)-2h; *ii*) the structure O_{2c}(2H,2S)-1a is more stable by 0.69 eV than O_{2c}(2H,2S)-2h; *iii*) the structure O_{2c}(1L,1R)-1a is more stable by 1.43 eV than O_{2c}(1L,1R)-1o.

Similarly to the discussed above models of ceria (111) surface and smaller ceria nanoparticle, no clear dependence of the structure stability and distances between two yttrium cations (blue squares in Fig. 2A) and the location of the dopant cations on surface or in subsurface positions (blue squares in Fig. 2B) is found. We also examined conceivable correlation of the relative stability with other characteristics of the models – the influence of the calculated electrostatic potentials at the cerium centers substituted by yttrium and the oxygen centers removed (Fig. S5A-C, ESI) and the average number of oxygen centers, surrounding two Y³⁺ cations (Fig. S5D, ESI). However, no obvious trends are found.

3.3.2 Oxygen vacancy in the nanoparticles containing two yttrium ions

We modeled 17 structures (Table 8), with an O vacancy created in the most stable found three structures $\text{Ce}_{38}\text{Y}_2\text{O}_{79}$, $\text{O}_{2c}(1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a}$, $\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{H},2\text{O})-1\text{a}$, $\text{O}_{2c}(1\text{F},2\text{H})-1\text{a}$, featuring different combinations of Y^{3+} cations: two surface, two subsurface and one surface and one subsurface, respectively. Not unexpectedly, it is most energetically favorable to create an O vacancy in low-coordinated positions at the small (100) facets. The most stable structure is $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{c}$ with two surface Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies in two most distant low-coordinated sites of one (100) facet. It is less favorable to remove both O centers from the neighbouring positions of a (100) facet: the corresponding structures $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{b}$ and $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{d}$ are less stable by 0.65 - 0.66 eV than structure $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{c}$. When the second vacancy is created in another (100) facet opposite to the first vacancy, the obtained structure $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{p}$ is less stable by only 0.08 eV than the most stable $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{c}$.

The lowest energy of the O vacancy formation in the latter structure is 0.9 eV, which is only slightly higher than the value calculated for the pristine $\text{Ce}_{40}\text{O}_{80}$ nanoparticle, 0.8 eV.^{28,29} The next in stability structure, $\text{O}_{2c}((2\text{H},2\text{O})-1\text{a})-1\text{p}$, is characterized by both Y^{3+} cations located in neighboring subsurface positions, whereas the both oxygen vacancy positions are the same as in $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{p}$. The former structure is less stable by only 0.06 eV than the $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{c}$ structure and features a similar O vacancy formation energy value. Other considered structures are less stable by ca. 0.3 eV and more than $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{c}$.

In the structures $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a})-1\text{p}$, $\text{O}_{2c}((2\text{H},2\text{O})-1\text{a})-1\text{k}$, $\text{O}_{2c}((2\text{H},2\text{O})-1\text{a})-1\text{p}$, $\text{O}_{4c}((2\text{H},2\text{O})-1\text{a})-2\text{h}$, $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{F},2\text{H})-1\text{a})-1\text{p}$ and $\text{O}_{2c}((1\text{F},2\text{H})-1\text{a})-2\text{e}$ one of the Ce^{3+} is located next to the created O vacancy, while another Ce^{3+} is far from the vacancies. In all other considered models both Ce^{3+} cations appear in the vicinity of the created O vacancy.

3.3.3 Stoichiometric $\text{Ce}_{40}\text{O}_{80}$ nanoparticle containing four yttrium ions

We considered 23 structures $\text{Ce}_{36}\text{Y}_4\text{O}_{78}$ containing two pairs of Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies (see Table 9). The most stable structure is $\text{O}_{2c}(1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a}/\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{H},2\text{S})-1\text{p}$. Other structures, which are built from two stable combinations of two Y^{3+} cations and one O vacancy, also result in stable arrangements, such as $\text{O}_{2c}(1\text{L},1\text{R})-1\text{a}/\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{H},2\text{S})-1\text{p}$, $\text{O}_{2c}(1\text{E},1\text{K})-1\text{a}/\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{H},2\text{O})-1\text{p}$ and $\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{H},2\text{O})-1\text{a}/\text{O}_{2c}(1\text{L},1\text{R})-1\text{p}$.

When both O centers are removed from one small (100) facet, it is not most favorable to remove them from two neighboring O sites. It is more favorable to remove two O centers diagonally located with respect to each other or those from two opposite (100) facets.

4. Summary and conclusions

We performed periodic density functional calculations of CeO₂(111) slab as well as one smaller, Ce₂₁O₄₂, and one larger, Ce₄₀O₈₀, nanoparticle models doped by two and four Y³⁺ cations. This substitution induces, respectively, formation of one and two O vacancies for charge compensation.

CeO₂(111) slab models. The most stable structures on the CeO₂(111) surface are calculated to be with Y³⁺ cations located on neighboring sites close to the oxygen vacancy created in the first or second subsurface layer.

The presence of Y³⁺ does not noticeably change the reducibility of ceria slab models for the most stable structures, when the vacancy is in the first subsurface layer. However, when the oxygen vacancy is created on the surface or in the second subsurface layer, the energies for O vacancy formation decrease by 0.2-0.3 eV in the presence of Y³⁺ cations compared to the corresponding values calculated for the pristine ceria system. This result is important from a practical point of view, since yttrium can increase the mobility of surface oxygen centers and in this way facilitate oxidation of adsorbates with their participation.

Our CeO₂(111) slab models with four Y³⁺ cations showed that there is no clear preference to whether both Y³⁺ pairs prefer to stay close to each other or separate. We also found that combining of two stable configurations of Y³⁺ pair and O vacancy one gets a stable structure.

When the dopant ions are on the surface layer, the basicity of surface oxygen centers around the dopant ions is slightly higher than that of the corresponding O centers on the surface of pristine ceria, as estimated by the O1s core level shifts. Differently, oxygen centers near the oxygen vacancy feature stabilization of their O1s levels, i.e. a lower basicity.

Ce₂₁O₄₂ smaller nanoparticle models. Our previous calculations showed that for pristine ceria nanoparticles of this kind O is most easily removed from the low(two)-coordinated sites.^{28,29} However, we were unable to confirm this observation for the doped Ce₁₉Y₂O₄₁ structures, where one O center is removed for charge compensation of the introduced two Y³⁺ cations. In the most stable structures containing yttrium dopants, oxygen centers are removed from the top two O layers: two-coordinated O centers from the (100) facet and four-coordinated O centers from the layer below. At variance from the doped ceria slab models, in these ceria nanoparticle models it seems to be not obligatory that both Y³⁺ cations are in neighboring positions near the O vacancy, likely due to higher structural flexibility of the nanoparticles. Our calculations showed that in the most stable structures Y³⁺ cations replace Ce⁴⁺ from the (100) facet or the layers beneath it, including the only subsurface cationic site.

Ce₄₀O₈₀ larger nanoparticle models. In the most stable structures O vacancies are created in the small (100) facets, where O centers are low-(two) coordinated. It is not favorable to remove four-coordinated O centers from subsurface regions. In such latter cases the energy of the structures is high or a surface O center moves to the subsurface vacancy during the geometry optimization and heals it. Y³⁺ cation is stable, when it replaces Ce⁴⁺ cations in the same coordination; it is not needed to remove an O center around the Y³⁺ cation. The presence of Y³⁺ dopants can insignificantly increase the O vacancy formation energy.

When four Y³⁺ cations are introduced in the nanoparticle it is not favorable for both O vacancies to be created in one (100) facet. In the most stable structures oxygen vacancies are located on different facets of the nanoparticle. The combinations of two stable positions for the Y³⁺ cations lead to a stable structure. There is no clear preference for Y³⁺ to be close to each other or well apart. This is also the case for the distance from Y³⁺ ions to O vacancies.

General conclusions. Our calculations demonstrate that the smaller is an yttrium-doped ceria system the less rules and trends can be elucidated regarding energetic and structural features of the most stable locations of the doping ions with respect to each other and to the created charge compensating O vacancies. In the slab models one can notice some trends for the preferred locations of Y³⁺ cations and the O vacancy. It is most stable for Y³⁺ to stay close to each other and for the created O vacancy to be in their immediate vicinity, both preferably in the subsurface region. On the contrary, the smaller Ce₂₁O₄₂ nanoparticle with various low-coordinated corner and edge sites exposed and the very flexible structure reveals a clear tendency neither for the location of Y³⁺ cations, nor for the O vacancy position. A quite similar statement can be made for the computational modeling results we obtained for the doped larger Ce₄₀O₈₀ nanoparticles. Yet, one trend is found for the latter regarding the location of the O vacancies, which are preferably formed on the small (100) facets, where less strongly bound two-coordinated O centers are available for the removal.

Also we found that in the structures with four Y³⁺ cations and two O vacancies, the most stable situations can be achieved by combining the positions obtained in the most stable structures with two Y³⁺ cations and one O vacancy.

Thus, the main effect of yttrium doping on the ceria slab model, representative for large ceria particles, is lowering of the oxygen vacancy formation energy for surface oxygen centers by ca. 0.3 eV, which thus becomes almost the same as the energy required for the formation of subsurface vacancy. In general, the yttrium doping of ceria has negligible effect on the reducibility of ceria surfaces and nanoparticles. One of the reasons can be the very similar ionic radii of Y³⁺ and Ce⁴⁺ ions, which differ by only 0.03 or 0.05 Å for 6- or 8-

coordinated ions, respectively.⁴³

On the other hand, the lack of preference for positions of yttrium cations and oxygen vacancies in the doped ceria nanoparticles combined with their flexibility would facilitate local rearrangement between structures of similar stability. This may be connected also with oxygen migration in those systems, which can enable dedicated usage of CeO₂-Y₂O₃ nanocomposites in catalytic applications.

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Figure 1. Top (upper panel) and side (lower panel)) views of $\text{CeO}_2(111)$ surface slab model displaying one unit cell. Each position of Ce cations replaced by an Y^{3+} cation is denoted with a number and a capital letter. The number indicates vertical position of the Ce cation: 1 – in the first (surface) cationic layer and 2 – in the second (subsurface) cationic layer, which is not visible in the upper panel, i.e. below an O anion in the first subsurface anionic layer. Capital letters are used to distinguish various surface and subsurface positions. The O vacancy created in the surface O layer, in the first or second subsurface O layers is marked as a green, blue or yellow circle, respectively. Color coding: Ce – yellow, O from the surface layer – dark red, O from the first subsurface layer – red, O from the second subsurface layer (located exactly below surface Ce atoms) – light red.

Figure 2. Relations between the relative stability of various calculated models and the nearest Y-Y distances (A) or the positions occupied by the two Y centers (B). Ceria surface – brown triangles, smaller nanoparticle – green bullets and larger nanoparticle – blue squares.

Figure 3. Top view of the initial structures of doped ceria surface used to model the formation of a second oxygen vacancy: A – $O_{SL}(1A,1B)$ structure, B – $O_{FS}(1B,2C)$ structure, C – $O_{SS}(2C,2D)$ structure. The first O vacancy is marked as a (green, blue or yellow) circle, see caption of Fig. 1. Each position of the second removed O atom is denoted with a number and a small letter. The number indicates vertical position of the removed O: 1 – from the first (surface) anionic layer, 2 – from the second (subsurface) anionic layer and 3 – from the third (right below a surface cation) anionic layer. Small letters are used to distinguish various surface and subsurface positions. Color coding: Ce – yellow, O from the surface layer – dark red, O from the first subsurface layer – red, O from the second subsurface layer – light red, Y – light blue. For clarity the Y-O bonds are shown.

Figure 4. Estimated O 1s core level energies for the pristine CeO₂(111) structure – green bullets, and for two structures with two yttrium ions each, O_{SL}(1A,1B) – blue rhombus and O_{SL}(2C,2D) – orange triangles.

Figure 5. Side and top views of $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle model. The positions of the cerium cations which are replaced by Y^{3+} are denoted with capital letters and numbers. The numbers indicate the position of the Ce cations at the surface or subsurface (only one Ce cation is in a subsurface position) regions. The created O vacancy is denoted with a small letter and the number indicates if the oxygen center is on/in the surface (1) or subsurface (2) position. Color coding: Ce – yellow, surface O centers – dark red, subsurface O centers – red.

Figure 6. Side (left column) and top (right column) views of the optimized models of the most stable structures of $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle with two Y^{3+} cations and one O vacancy: a) $\text{O}_{4c}(2\text{I},1\text{H})\text{-}2\text{h}$; b) $\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{I},1\text{A})\text{-}1\text{a}$; c) $\text{O}_{2c}(2\text{I},1\text{H})\text{-}1\text{a}$. Color coding: Ce – yellow, surface O centers – dark red, subsurface O centers – red, Y – light blue. For clarity the Y-O bonds are shown.

Figure 7. Side (left column) and top (right column) views of the optimized models of the most stable structures of $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ nanoparticle with four Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies: a) $\text{O}_{2c}(1L,1F)-1m/\text{O}_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$; b) $\text{O}_{2c}(1K,1F)-1m/\text{O}_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$; c) $\text{O}_{2c}(1L,1F)-1m/\text{O}_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$. Color coding: Ce – yellow, surface O centers – dark red, subsurface O centers – red, Y – light blue. For clarity the Y-O bonds are shown.

Table 1. Energetic (in eV), structural (in pm) and coordination characteristics of the modeled CeO₂(111) structures containing each two Y³⁺ cations and one O vacancy, either in the surface (O_{SL}), first subsurface (O_{FS}) or second subsurface (O_{SS}) layers.

Structure ^a	E _{rel} ^b	Y-Y ^c	Y-O _{vac} ^d	N ^e	M ^f
<i>O_{SL}(1A,1B)</i>	0.32	421	260, 263	6, 6	1
<i>O_{SL}(1B,2C)</i>	0.33	384	263, 456	6, 8	2
<i>O_{SL}(2C,2D)</i>	0.40	375	458, 460	8, 8	2
<i>O_{SL}(2E,2F)</i>	0.67	378	893, 894	8, 8	2
<i>O_{SL}(2E,2G)</i>	0.68	376	895, 1041	8, 8	2
O _{SL} (1H,2G)	0.79	662	890, 1042	7, 8	0
<i>O_{SL}(2F,1H)</i>	0.83	381	889, 893	8, 7	2
O _{SL} (1I,1J)	0.86	1137	596, 609	7, 7	0
<i>O_{SL}(1H,1J)</i>	1.00	375	600, 887	7, 7	2
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)</i>	0.00	410	252, 256	6, 7	1
<i>O_{FS}(2C,2D)</i>	0.02	378	257, 448	7, 8	2
<i>O_{FS}(1A,1B)</i>	0.26	409	250, 253	6, 6	1
<i>O_{FS}(2E,2F)</i>	0.37	378	706, 801	8, 8	2
<i>O_{FS}(2E,2G)</i>	0.40	378	803, 1038	8, 8	2
O _{FS} (1H,2G)	0.51	661	799, 801	7, 8	0
<i>O_{FS}(2F,1H)</i>	0.52	380	706, 800	8, 7	2
O _{FS} (1I,1J)	0.63	1156	591, 596	7, 7	0
<i>O_{FS}(1H,1J)</i>	0.73	376	595, 799	7, 7	2
<i>O_{SS}(2C,2D)</i>	0.02	406	249, 252	7, 7	1
<i>O_{SS}(1B,2C)</i>	0.38	420	249, 265	6, 7	1
<i>O_{SS}(2E,2F)</i>	0.49	379	593, 594	8, 8	2
<i>O_{SS}(2E,2G)</i>	0.55	376	595, 798	8, 8	2
<i>O_{SS}(2F,1H)</i>	0.72	377	593, 701	8, 7	2
O _{SS} (1H,2G)	0.73	660	703, 799	7, 8	0
<i>O_{SS}(1A,1B)</i>	0.83	377	266, 442	7, 6	2
O _{SS} (1I,1J)	0.91	1147	448, 797	7, 7	0
<i>O_{SS}(1H,1J)</i>	0.93	381	448, 700	7, 7	2

^a Position of Y³⁺ cations as shown in Fig. 1. Structure names in italics indicate that Y³⁺ cations are located in nearest-neighboring positions. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure O_{FS}(1B,2C). ^c Distance between two nearest Y cations. ^d Distances between Y atoms and the O vacancy position. ^e Coordination numbers of Y³⁺ with respect to O atoms. ^f Number of O atoms bound simultaneously with the both Y³⁺ cations.

Table 2. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) characteristics of the modeled Y-doped CeO₂(111) surface structures each containing two Y cations and two O vacancies.

Structures ^a	E _{rel} ^b	E _{vac} ^c	O _{vac} -O _{vac} ^d	#Ce ^e
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-1a	0.41	2.61	389	39, 40
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-2g	0.55	2.75	1179	13, 48
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-1b	0.60	2.80	656	47, 48
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-1c	0.60	2.80	389	15, 16
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-3j	0.63	2.83	1014	47, 48
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-2f	0.75	2.94	482	27, 31
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-3h	0.90	3.10	388	16, 20
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-2e	0.92	3.12	242	15, 16
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-2d	1.02	3.21	233	31, 40
O _{SL} (1A,1B)-3i	1.05	3.25	386	20, 31
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-2f	0.00	2.52	391	27, 39
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-1c	0.14	2.65	606	6, 16
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-2e	0.15	2.67	388	4, 16
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-1a	0.25	2.76	247	39, 40
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-3j	0.29	2.80	811	47, 48
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-2g	0.30	2.82	1009	13, 47
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-3k	0.72	3.24	255	1, 30
O _{FS} (1B,2C)-3i	0.76	3.28	248	4, 32
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-2g	0.10	2.61	974	13, 48
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-1c	0.18	2.70	662	6, 15
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-2e	0.23	2.75	463	4, 16
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-3i	0.38	2.90	385	4, 20
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-3j	0.45	2.97	764	42, 48
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-3l	0.47	2.98	386	18, 27
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-2d	0.53	3.05	241	3, 4
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-1a	0.53	3.05	397	39, 40
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-2f	0.71	3.23	243	26, 27
O _{SS} (2C,2D)-4a	0.78	3.30	253	30, 35

^a Positions of the second O vacancy in the most stable O_{SL}(1A,1B), O_{FS}(1B,2C), O_{SS}(2C,2D) structures (see Fig. 1, Table 1) are denoted with small letters shown in Figs. 2-4 and numbers. The numbers specify positions of the removed O: 1 – in the first (surface) layer, 2 – in the second (subsurface) layer, 3 – in the third (below surface Ce or Y cation) layer. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure O_{FS}(1B,2C)-2f. ^c O vacancy formation energy. ^d Distance between two O vacancies. ^e Positions of the Ce³⁺ cations (see numbers in Fig. S1).

Table 3. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) characteristics of CeO₂(111) structures containing each four Y³⁺ cations and two O vacancies.

Structures ^a	E _{rel} ^b	Y-Y ^c	ΔY-Y ^d
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{SL}(1A,1N)</i>	0.64	414; 421	4
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{FS}(1A,1N)</i>	0.19	407; 399	-3
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{SS}(2D,2Q)</i>	0.51	461; 402	51
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{SL}(1A,1L)</i>	0.80	408; 455	-2
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{FS}(1H,2F)</i>	0.00	408; 410	-2
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{FS}(1R,2M)</i>	0.10	408; 409	-2
<i>O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{FS}(1S,2T)</i>	0.14	410; 408	0
<i>O_{SS}(2C,2D)/O_{SS}(1N,1B)</i>	0.64	404; 417	-2
<i>O_{SS}(2C,2D)/O_{SS}(1L,2K)</i>	0.37	396; 421	-10
<i>O_{SS}(2C,2D)/O_{SS}(2K,2M)</i>	0.05	396; 407	-10
<i>O_{SS}(2C,2D)/O_{SS}(2E,2F)</i>	0.01	405; 406	-1
<i>O_{SS}(2C,2D)/O_{SS}(2M,2Q)</i>	0.10	408; 399	2

^a Positions of Y³⁺ cations as shown in Fig. 1. Structure names in italics indicate that both Y³⁺ pairs are located close to each other. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure O_{FS}(1B,2C)/O_{FS}(1H,2F). ^c Distances between two nearest Y cations. ^d Difference between the Y-Y distance in the structure with four Y³⁺ cations and the structures with two Y³⁺ cations O_{FS}(1B,2C) (410 pm) and O_{SS}(2C,2D) (406 pm), respectively.

Table 4. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) and coordination characteristics of the smaller ceria nanoparticle $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ structures containing each two Y^{3+} cations and one O vacancy.

Structure ^a	E_{rel}^b	Y-Y ^c	Y-O _{vac} ^d	N ^e	M ^f
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1B)-1b</i>	0.31	412	215, 214	5, 5	1
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1E)-1a</i>	0.39	345	215, 540	5, 5	2
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1H)-1a</i>	0.16	359	215, 404	5, 6	2
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1a</i>	0.15	402	215, 215	5, 5	1
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1m</i>	1.59	339	771, 1005	5, 5	2
<i>O_{2c}(1D,1E)-1d</i>	0.40	817	214, 778	5, 5	0
<i>O_{2c}(1D,1E)-1o</i>	1.07	800	817, 553	6, 5	0
<i>O_{2c}(1E,1F)-1b</i>	0.39	358	533, 373	5, 6	2
<i>O_{2c}(1E,1F)-1i</i>	1.01	357	211, 411	4, 6	2
<i>O_{2c}(1E,1H)-1a</i>	0.37	362	540, 404	5, 6	1
<i>O_{2c}(1K,1L)-1m</i>	0.36	398	215, 215	4, 4	1
<i>O_{2c}(1K,1E)-1i</i>	1.21	436	223, 211	4, 4	1
<i>O_{2c}(1K,1M)-1n</i>	0.82	419	211, 216	4, 5	1
<i>O_{2c}(1J,1H)-1a</i>	0.13	740	714, 404	6, 6	0
<i>O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a</i>	0.03	397	477, 215	7, 5	1
<i>O_{2c}(2I,1F)-1b</i>	0.08	420	465, 373	7, 6	0
<i>O_{2c}(2I,1H)-1a</i>	0.04	381	477, 404	7, 6	1
<i>O_{2c}(2I,1M)-1a</i>	0.44	361	477, 690	7, 6	1
<i>O_{2c}(2I,1M)-1o</i>	0.62	360	440, 215	8, 5	2
<i>O_{3c}(1A,1E)-1f</i>	1.24	392	239,228	5, 4	1
<i>O_{3c}(1A,1H)-1f</i>	1.01	394	239, 228	5, 5	1
<i>O_{3c}(1M,1N)-1l</i>	0.55	555	223, 223	5, 5	0
<i>O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h</i>	0.00	399	244, 228	7, 5	1
<i>O_{4c}(2I,1A)-2h</i>	0.19	410	244, 230	7, 5	1
<i>O_{4c}(1D,1E)-2h</i>	0.52	793	421, 433	6, 5	0
<i>O_{4c}(2I,1F)-2g</i>	0.08	420	236, 221	7, 6	0

^a Position of Y^{3+} cations as shown in Fig. 5. Structure names in italics indicate that Y^{3+} cations are located in nearest-neighboring positions. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure $\text{O}_{4c}(2\text{I},1\text{H})-2\text{h}$. ^c Distance between two nearest Y cations. ^d Distances between Y atoms and the O vacancy position. ^e Coordination numbers of Y^{3+} with respect to O atoms. ^f Number of O atoms bound simultaneously with the both Y^{3+} cations.

Table 5. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) characteristics of the modeled structures of the smaller ceria nanoparticle Ce₂₁O₄₂ each containing two Y³⁺ cations and two O vacancies.

Structures ^a	E _{rel} ^b	E _{vac} ^c	O _{vac} -O _{vac} ^d	#Ce ^e
O _{2c} (O _{2c} (2I,1A)-1a)-1c	0.00	1.87	459	1, 4
O _{2c} (O _{2c} (2I,1A)-1a)-1b	0.46	2.33	319	1, 19
O _{2c} (O _{2c} (2I,1A)-1a)-1d	0.42	2.29	319	4, 13
O _{2c} (O _{2c} (2I,1A)-1a)-1i	0.21	2.08	742	2, 10
O _{2c} (O _{4c} (2I,1H)-2h)-1a	0.97	2.85	262	13, 18
O _{2c} (O _{4c} (2I,1H)-2h)-1b	0.38	2.25	379	1, 18
O _{2c} (O _{4c} (2I,1H)-2h)-1c	0.16	2.03	486	1, 4
O _{2c} (O _{4c} (2I,1H)-2h)-1d	0.30	2.18	379	4, 13
O _{2c} (O _{4c} (2I,1H)-2h)-1o	0.85	2.72	527	7, 11
O _{2c} (O _{4c} (2I,1H)-2h)-1i	0.14	2.01	613	2, 10

^a The letters indicate the positions of Y³⁺ and removed O centers shown in Fig. 5, while the numbers indicate whether the Y³⁺ or removed O is located at the first (surface) layer, 1, or second (subsurface) layer, 2. In the parentheses is shown the structure with two Y³⁺ and one O_{vac} from which the O center is removed. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure O_{2c}(O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a)-1c. ^c O vacancy formation energy. ^d Distance between two O vacancies. ^e Positions of the Ce³⁺ cations (see numbers in Fig. S2).

Table 6. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) characteristics of the smaller ceria nanoparticle $\text{Ce}_{21}\text{O}_{42}$ structures containing four Y^{3+} cations and two O vacancies ($\text{Ce}_{17}\text{Y}_4\text{O}_{40}$).

Structure ^a	E_{rel}^b	Y-Y ^c	$\Delta\text{Y-Y}^d$
<i>$O_{2c}(1B,1A)-1b/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	0.40	397, 408	9
<i>$O_{2c}(1B,1D)-1c/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	0.19	400, 395	-4
<i>$O_{2c}(1E,1F)-1b/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	0.66	356, 407	8
$O_{2c}(1K,1L)-1b/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$	1.88	338, 408	9
$O_{2c}(1K,1L)-1m/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$	0.23	400, 400	1
<i>$O_{2c}(1K,1F)-1m/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	0.04	354, 399	0
<i>$O_{2c}(1L,1F)-1m/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	0.00	354, 401	2
<i>$O_{2c}(1L,1F)-1j/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	0.67	382, 401	2
$O_{2c}(1L,1G)-1j/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$	0.86	437, 401	2
<i>$O_{2c}(1M,1O)-1o/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	0.95	393, 396	-3
<i>$O_{4c}(1M,1O)-2k/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$</i>	2.60	369, 432	33
<i>$O_{2c}(1B,1J)-1b/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	0.88	348, 443	46
<i>$O_{2c}(1B,1J)-1c/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	0.39	364, 383	-14
<i>$O_{2c}(1G,1J)-1b/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	1.11	355, 449	52
<i>$O_{2c}(1G,1J)-1c/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	0.47	361, 376	-21
<i>$O_{2c}(1K,1E)-1i/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	1.01	439, 398	1
$O_{2c}(1K,1L)-1m/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$	0.18	404, 398	1
$O_{2c}(1L,1G)-1j/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$	0.92	440, 398	1
<i>$O_{2c}(1L,1F)-1m/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	0.04	352, 393	-4
<i>$O_{2c}(1G,1F)-1b/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	1.06	356, 417	20
<i>$O_{3c}(1G,1F)-1e/O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$</i>	1.26	397, 390	-7
<i>$O_{2c}(1B,1D)-1c/O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1a$</i>	0.38	403, 403	1
$O_{2c}(1K,1L)-1m/O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1a$	0.29	402, 403	1
$O_{2c}(1G,1L)-1j/O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1a$	1.09	442, 410	8
$O_{2c}(1G,1J)-1j/O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1a$	0.88	346, 410	8

^a Position of Y^{3+} and O^{2-} ions are shown in Fig. 5. Structure names in italic indicate that both Y^{3+} pairs are located close to each other. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure $O_{2c}(1L,1F)-1m/O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$. ^c Distances between two nearest Y cations. ^d Difference between the Y-Y distance in the structures with two Y^{3+} ($O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h$ 399 pm; $O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a$ – 397 pm; $O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1a$ – 402 pm) and the structure with four Y^{3+} cations.

Table 7. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) and coordination characteristics of the larger ceria nanoparticle Ce₄₀O₈₀ structures containing each two Y³⁺ cations and one vacancy.

Structure ^a	E _{rel} ^b	Y-Y ^c	Y-O _{vac} ^d	N ^e	M ^f
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1B)-1a</i>	0.65	419	219; 214	5, 5	1
<i>O_{2c}(1A,2H)-1a</i>	0.44	370	219; 446	5, 8	2
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1L)-1a</i>	0.44	976	219; 900	5, 4	0
<i>O_{2c}(1A,2S)-1a</i>	0.56	829	219; 945	5, 8	0
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1G)-1a</i>	1.05	369	219; 567	5, 5	2
<i>O_{2c}(1E,1K)-1a</i>	0.00	1034	545; 789	6, 6	0
<i>O_{2c}(1B,1E)-1a</i>	0.32	354	214; 545	5, 6	2
<i>O_{2c}(1F,1M)-1g</i>	0.50	383	408; 214	7, 5	2
<i>O_{2c}(1F,2H)-1a</i>	0.28	375	408; 446	7, 8	2
<i>O_{2c}(2H,2O)-1a</i>	0.28	372	446; 680	8, 8	2
<i>O_{2c}(2H,2S)-1a</i>	0.29	540	446; 945	8, 8	0
<i>O_{2c}(1L,1M)-1a</i>	0.85	731	900; 214	6, 4	0
<i>O_{2c}(1L,1R)-1a</i>	0.32	1509	900; 1134	4, 4	0
<i>O_{2c}(1B,1D)-1a</i>	1.87	522	214; 453	5, 6	0
<i>O_{2c}(1B,1D)-1p</i>	0.86	505	1212; 1275	6, 6	0
<i>O_{3c}(1L,1R)-1o</i>	1.75	1522	1437; 213	3, 4	0
<i>O_{3c}(1A,1G)-1f</i>	1.92	429	242; 241	5, 5	2
<i>O_{4c}(1L,1R)-2e</i>	0.32	1509	752; 983	4, 4	0
<i>O_{4c}(1A,1B)-2e</i>	0.64	419	232; 232	5, 5	1
<i>O_{4c}(1F,2H)-2e</i>	0.36	400	232; 230	6, 7	1
<i>O_{4c}(2H,2O)-2h</i>	0.79	395	233; 233	8, 8	1
<i>O_{4c}(2H,2O)-2e</i>	0.27	372	232; 376	8, 9	2
<i>O_{4c}(2H,2S)-2h</i>	0.98	537	233; 446	8, 8	0
<i>O_{4c}(2O,2Q)-2l</i>	0.61	372	233; 229	7, 7	1
<i>O_{4c}(2O,2P)-2l</i>	0.98	537	233; 445	8, 7	0
<i>O_{4c}(2O,2N)-2h</i>	0.61	395	233; 229	7, 7	1

^a Positions of Y³⁺ cations as shown in Fig. 8. Structure names in italics indicate that Y³⁺ cations are located in nearest-neighboring positions. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure O_{2c}(1E,1K)-1a. ^c Distance between two nearest Y cations. ^d Distances between Y cations and the O vacancy position. ^e Coordination numbers of Y³⁺ with respect to O atoms. ^f Number of O atoms bound simultaneously with the both Y³⁺ cations.

Table 8. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) characteristics of the modeled structures of the larger Ce₄₀O₈₀ nanoparticle containing each two Y³⁺ cations and two O vacancies.

Structures ^a	E _{rel} ^b	E _{vac} ^c	O _{vac} -O _{vac} ^d	#Ce ^e
CeO ₂ -1a		0.76		9, 12
CeO ₂ -1b		1.51		2, 3
CeO ₂ -1c		1.52		3, 4
CeO ₂ -1d		1.53		1, 4
CeO ₂ -1k		1.60		7, 10
CeO ₂ -1p		1.53		14, 15
CeO ₂ -2h		1.81		5, 12
O _{2c} ((1E,1K)-1a)-1b	0.66	1.61	319	5, 3
O _{2c} ((1E,1K)-1a)-1c	0.00	0.95	449	3, 4
O _{2c} ((1E,1K)-1a)-1d	0.65	1.60	315	1, 4
O _{2c} ((1E,1K)-1a)-1k	0.40	1.35	765	7, 10
O _{2c} ((1E,1K)-1a)-1p	0.08	1.03	1304	13, 14
O _{2c} ((2H,2O)-1a)-1b	0.94	1.89	319	3, 5
O _{2c} ((2H,2O)-1a)-1c	0.36	1.31	449	3, 8
O _{2c} ((2H,2O)-1a)-1d	0.99	1.94	315	1, 8
O _{2c} ((2H,2O)-1a)-1k	0.29	1.24	765	7, 11
O _{2c} ((2H,2O)-1a)-1p	0.06	1.01	1304	9, 14
O _{4c} ((2H,2O)-1a)-2h	1.00	1.95	517	5, 6
O _{2c} ((1F,2H)-1a)-1b	0.92	1.87	319	2, 3
O _{2c} ((1F,2H)-1a)-1c	0.40	1.35	449	3, 8
O _{2c} ((1F,2H)-1a)-1d	1.02	1.97	315	1, 8
O _{2c} ((1F,2H)-1a)-1k	0.68	1.63	765	7, 10
O _{2c} ((1F,2H)-1a)-1p	0.34	1.29	1304	13, 14
O _{2c} ((1F,2H)-1a)-2e	1.50	2.45	255	2, 5

^a Positions of Y³⁺ and removed O centers shown in Fig. 8, while the numbers indicate whether the Y³⁺ or removed O are located at the surface region, 1, or subsurface region, 2. In the parentheses is shown the structure with two Y³⁺ and one O_{vac} from which the O center is removed. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure O_{2c}((1E,1K)-1a)-1c. ^c O vacancy formation energy. ^d Distance between two O vacancies. ^e Positions of the Ce³⁺ cations (see numbers in Fig. S2).

Table 9. Energetic (in eV) and structural (in pm) characteristics of the larger ceria nanoparticle Ce₄₀O₈₀ structures containing each four Y³⁺ cations and two O vacancies (Ce₃₆Y₄O₇₈).

Structure ^a	E _{rel} ^b	Y-Y ^c	ΔY-Y ^d
O _{2c} (1E,1K)-1a/O _{2c} (1F,2H)-1p	0.34	1034; 369	0
O _{2c} (1E,1K)-1a/O _{2c} (2H,2O)-1p	0.21	1034; 371	0
O _{2c} (1E,1K)-1a/O _{2c} (2H,2S)-1p	0.00	1034; 531	0
O _{2c} (1E,1K)-1a/O _{2c} (1L,1R)-1p	0.38	1041; 1512	7
O _{2c} (1E,1K)-1a/O _{2c} (1B,1D)-1p	1.17	1032; 529	-2
O _{2c} (1F,2H)-1a/O _{2c} (1L,1R)-1p	0.36	372; 1512	-3
O _{2c} (1F,2H)-1a/O _{2c} (2Q,2N)-1p	0.28	372; 521	-3
O _{2c} (1F,2H)-1a/O _{2c} (2O,2N)-1p	0.52	367; 368	-8
O _{2c} (1L,1R)-1a/O _{2c} (2H,2S)-1p	0.15	1512; 531	3
O _{2c} (2H,2O)-1a/O _{2c} (1G,1M)-1g	0.78	373; 412	1
O _{2c} (2H,2O)-1a/O _{2c} (1L,1R)-1p	0.29	372; 1512	0
O _{2c} (2H,2O)-1a/O _{2c} (1L,1R)-1b	0.44	379; 1513	7
<i>O_{2c}(2H,2O)-1a/O_{2c}(2Q,2N)-1c</i>	0.52	374; 518	2
<i>O_{2c}(2H,2O)-1a/O_{2c}(2Q,2N)-1p</i>	0.32	368; 519	-4
<i>O_{2c}(2H,2O)-1a/O_{2c}(2S,2P)-1n</i>	0.59	370; 370	-2
<i>O_{2c}(2H,2O)-1a/O_{2c}(2S,2P)-1p</i>	0.51	373; 372	1
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1G)-1a/O_{2c}(1I,1F)-1p</i>	1.95	351; 528	-18
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1B)-1a/O_{2c}(1C,1D)-1c</i>	1.30	422; 423	3
<i>O_{2c}(1A,1B)-1a/O_{2c}(1C,1D)-1p</i>	3.23	418; 347	-1
O _{2c} (1A,1B)-1a/O _{2c} (1R,1L)-1c	0.50	426; 1510	7
O _{2c} (1A,1B)-1a/O _{2c} (1R,1L)-1d	1.24	420; 1510	1
O _{2c} (1A,1B)-1a/O _{2c} (1R,1L)-1p	0.80	418; 1510	-1
O _{2c} (1A,1B)-1a/O _{2c} (1U,1T)-1p	1.14	417; 416	-2

^a Positions of the corresponding letters are shown in Fig. 8. Structure names in italics indicate that both Y³⁺ pairs are located close to each other. ^b Relative energy with respect to the most stable structure O_{2c}(1E,1K)-1a/O_{2c}(2H,2S)-1p. ^c Distance between two Y nearest cations. ^d Difference between the Y-Y distance in the structure with two Y³⁺ (O_{4c}(2I,1H)-2h 399 pm; O_{2c}(2I,1A)-1a – 397 pm; O_{2c}(1A,1C)-1a – 402 pm) and the structure with four Y³⁺ cations.

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